

D8.7 Final Dissemination Report

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List of abbreviations

<Abbreviation>	<Explanation>
DoW	Description of Work
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FP7	Seventh Framework Programme
GESIS	GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
Gov2u	Government To You
HS	Hansard Society
ITI	University of Southampton IT Innovation
KMI	Open University, Knowledge Media Institute
UKOM	University Koblenz – Landau
SU	Stockholm University
M1	Month 1, M3=Month 3 etc.
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
MP	Member of Parliament
MS	Member States
Y1	Year 1
Y2	Year 2
Y3	Year 3
WP	Work Package
WPs	Work Packages
D8.5	D8.5 Dissemination Report (M12)
D8.6	D8.6 Dissemination Report (M24)
D8.3	D8.3 Project dissemination materials (M36)
D8.7	D8.7 Final Dissemination Report (M39)

Executive summary

According to the DoW description of WP8 (p.26-29), the main goal of WP8 Dissemination and Exploitation is to disseminate the findings of the project effectively, to engage key stakeholders for knowledge sharing and raise awareness about the SENSE4US tool, to launch an effective internal and external communications strategy to achieve the project's objectives as a consortium and, of course, provide assistance to other Work Packages (WPs) about dissemination issues.

The current document "D8.7 Final Report on dissemination activities", submitted in M39 (December 2016), is the second update of D8.5 "Report on dissemination activities" which was submitted in M12 after the completion of the project's first year.

D8.7 refers to the dissemination and communication objectives and strategy that was followed from October 2015 (M25) to December 2016 (M39), reports on the dissemination tools that were used for the project's promotion and the activities that were undertaken by partners during the same period.

As described in the deliverable, partners focused their efforts on participating in various events relevant to the project and giving presentations of the project as well as on papers' writing and papers' submission to major conferences, while project materials were created for further dissemination of the project and social media presence was significant during Y3 of the project.

During Y3 the project was focused on the engagement of the users in the project's solution and communication of its findings externally. Finally, some conclusions complete the deliverable's structure.

1 Introduction

1.1 The project: SENSE4US

SENSE4US was a project with 39 months lifetime, launched in October 2013 and ended in December 2016, co-funded under the Seventh Framework Programme (FP7-ICT-2013-10). It aims to assist policy makers in their tasks, by giving them the tools and methodology to access a wide array of current data and take into account the views of citizens on policy issues in real time.

Making and implementing policy at any level of government is fraught with difficulty. The impact of decisions made is not always obvious at the time the policy is formulated or enacted and any short-comings of the policy become known too late. Obviously the policy is always subject to change, however policy making is a long process and the cycle between new policy adopted and consequences felt take a long time. Therefore the challenge is to make effective policies and to adhere to most factors that is possible, what in the age of information can be difficult. This is not only due to the lack of proper information but also due to the difficulty of finding and aggregating the right data out of the sea of information which characterizes our modern world. Having once formulated a policy it is then impossible to make useful predictions around its likely impact and effectiveness. Besides, policy specialists lack the resources and the methodology to be able to access most current data and are out of reach to ultimately take into account the views of citizens on policy issues expressed in real time through social network discussions.

As specialists currently have to rely on readily available public information sources based on historic, rather than current data and consultation with a select group of consultants, SENSE4US project created a toolkit to support them in information gathering, analyzing and policy modeling in real time. This package of utilities is based on cutting-edge research.

The project's tools are directed to allow:

- the extraction of information from big data and open data sources;
- the automatic annotation and linkage of homogeneous data;
- the lexical analysis of sources and validation;
- the creation of policy models combining quantitative open data sources with qualitative social comments;
- the prediction of social impact of policy and the outcome of policy, providing understandable visualizations;
- and social network analysis for tracking discussion dynamics in social media.

Through close interaction with policy makers around Europe, the SENSE4US project validates results in complex policy-making settings and directs the research towards the support of more effective and better understood policy development.

The ultimate objective of the SENSE4US project is to advance policy modelling and simulation, data analytics and social network discussion dynamics, providing economic and social benefits at all policy making levels across Europe.

1.2 WP8 Dissemination and Exploitation

WP8 is a subset of the project and, according to the DoW (p.26), the Work Package (WP) that dedicates its efforts in promoting and communicating the project widely at local, national and European level, its objectives and its findings. WP8 strategy is two-fold focused on the project's dissemination and exploitation in the long-term.

As during the first 24 months of the project, WP8 continued to use a series of online and offline tools in order to raise awareness about the project and also manage to involve key stakeholders such as projects of relevant thematic field of activity and policy- and decision-makers at European level. Undoubtedly, WP8 work is highly dependent on partners' individual dissemination efforts meaning authorship of research publications, attendance and presentations during conferences and events, face-to-face meetings with influential stakeholders, etc. that ensure better dissemination and effective promotion of the project.

The long term sustainability and the effective exploitation of the project is undoubtedly linked directly with partners' full involvement and strong engagement in WP8.

The dissemination and communication strategy of WP8 was set in the first year of the project explaining clearly the methods, the tools that would be used and the activities to be undertaken in order to achieve its objectives and give widespread visibility to project's developments and results.

The current deliverable is based on the D8.4 Dissemination Plan (M6) and its updates in D8.5 Dissemination Report (M12) and in D8.6 Dissemination Plan (M24) and it presents all the activities performed during Y3 (October 2015 – December 2016).

1.3 The deliverable: scope, methodology, structure and audience

1.3.1 Scope

The scope of the deliverable is to update the yearly report of the dissemination and communication of the project by consortium partners. The deliverable offers an update on tools (project website, social media, newsletters, publications, etc.) and activities that were undertaken towards the WP8 objectives during the last 15 months (M25-M39) of project's implementation.

1.3.2 Methodology

As also mentioned in D8.5 and D8.6 deliverables, the methodology that was followed for the production of this deliverable was based on the constructive collaboration of WP8 leader with the project partners. The collaborative efforts of all partners are of utmost importance since they will result in the very best version of the deliverable.

The first draft of this report was created by Government to You (Gov2u), WP8 Leader, based on the input received by partners. SENSE4US partners were asked to provide the necessary contributions related to the activities they undertook during the reporting period. The final editing has been done by Gov2u and all input received from partners was incorporated. The final version will be submitted to the project coordinator, who will in turn submit it to the European Commission (EC).

1.3.3 Structure

Regarding the structure of the report, it comprises of five main parts:

- the first section makes a short introduction to the project (type of project, objectives, scope, and methodology) in order to help the reader to easier understand about the project's identity without being necessary to look into the previous submitted reports;
- the second section presents a summary of the dissemination activities made in Y1 and Y2 of project's implementation
- the third section focuses on an overview of the objectives achieved in Y3 (October 2015 – December 2016);
- the fourth section presents the dissemination and communication tools and activities for Y3 (October 2015 – December 2016);
- the last section refers to some conclusions.

1.3.4 Intended audience

The intended audience of this deliverable remains the same as defined in D8.5 and D8.6:

<i>Group of readers</i>	<i>Reasons for reading</i>
SENSE4US consortium partners	To be informed about the dissemination activities performed by the consortium during the reporting period (M25-M39)
Target groups: general public, research and scientific community, potential new end-users, possible dissemination partners, project stakeholders	To be informed about dissemination activities performed within the reporting period and raise awareness about the project, announce project objectives, further develop a community of interest
Representatives of organizations and institutions involved in similar projects or initiatives.	To share knowledge, information and best practices that can be adopted and utilized in similar projects
European Commission	This document is a deliverable of the SENSE4US project

Table 1 : Intended audience

1.4 Relation of the deliverable to other WP8 deliverables

This document is related directly to the following deliverables of WP8:

- [D8.1 Project dissemination materials \(M6\)](#)
- [D8.2 Project dissemination materials \(M12\)](#)
- [D8.4 Dissemination Plan \(M6\)](#)
- [D8.5 Report on dissemination activities \(M12\)](#)
- [D8.6 Report on dissemination activities \(M24\)](#)
- [D8.3 Project dissemination materials \(M39\)](#)

1.5 Quality management

Given that this report is an update of D8.5 and D8.6, its main parts are consistent to the previous ones approved by partners. Therefore, Gov2u asked for partners' contribution and their reporting on their dissemination activities undertaken during Y3 (October 2015 – December 2016) of project's implementation, prepared the updated draft of the report and shared it with partners. The deliverable uses the correct project template and a language quality control has been performed.

2 Summaries of previous dissemination activities

2.1 Summary of activities for Y1

This section briefly describes the dissemination activities that were made by the SENSE4US consortium during the first year of project’s implementation. A detailed report was provided in D8.5 (M12)

- Creation of the project website (www.sense4us.eu) which was launched in M1.
- Creation of the project logo
- Adding links from other sites to the project website
- Publication of articles and references about the project on other websites
- Creation of the project flyer
- Creation of the project poster
- Creation of the factsheet
- Publication of press releases
- Publication of articles and announcements about the project in media
- Presentations in conferences/ third party events
- Liaison with other similar projects

Type of activity	Number
Papers, article presentations	14
Organization of and participation in events, workshops, conferences	19
Newsletter Issues	1
Project Presentation	3
Press Coverage	20

Table 2 : Summary of activities for Y1

2.2 Summary of activities for Y2

This section briefly describes the dissemination activities that were made by the SENSE4US consortium during the second year of project’s implementation. A detailed report was provided in D8.6 (M24)

- Project’s website maintenance
- Adding links from other sites to the project website
- Publication of articles and references about the project on other websites
- Creation of the project brochure
- Creation of the project poster
- Creation of the factsheet
- Publication of press releases
- Publication of articles and announcements about the project in media
- Presentations in conferences/ third party events
- Liaison with other similar projects

<i>Type of activity</i>	<i>Number</i>
Papers, article presentations	18
Organization of and participation in events, workshops, conferences	16
Newsletter Issues	4
Project Presentation	1
Press Coverage	14

Table 3 : Summary of activities for Y2

3 Dissemination and Communication objectives for the reporting period

This section outlines the dissemination and communication objectives implemented for the reporting period (M25-M39). From October 2015 to December 2016, WP8 partners strived to achieve the following objectives:

- Expand the visibility of the project in social media and among relevant projects;
- Establish, maintain and enhance collaboration with other EU funded projects in the same domain by inviting them by email to introduce the project and find common fields of collaboration as well as by organizing events in common;
- Creation of synergies and knowledge sharing as well as co-organization of events that would communicate our developments to broader audiences;
- Further and most targeted promotion of the project, awareness raising widely, visibility via online and offline activities;
- Face-to-face contacts with stakeholders (MEPs, national representatives, Ministers, policy officers, etc.);
- Enhancement of networking based on latest developments and objectives of the project and excellent reputation itself to attract a wide circle of interested stakeholders with a legitimate interest in the outcome of the project;
- Increase the number of social media involvement via more posts and tweets related to the project as well as the number of people visiting the project's website;
- Participation in events at national and European level to raise awareness and visibility for the project;
- Facilitate WP8 communication and collaboration as well as assist consortium partners with their dissemination activities;
- Provide the deliverables and reports corresponding to the reporting period M25-M39;
- Monitoring of project website and social media profiles.

4 Dissemination and Communication tools and activities for the reporting period

An overview of the dissemination tools and activities that were used by the SENSE4US partners in order to raise the visibility of the project is provided in this chapter.

Dissemination tools are somewhat the vehicles that are being used to transport the most important messages, while activities are the concrete actions by which these tools could possibly be implemented.

4.1 Dissemination and communication tools

This section presents the dissemination tools used during the reporting period. These tools are the means through which the project’s main messages were transmitted and communicated outside of the consortium. A common branding was used throughout promotional materials with the intention of maintaining a consistent and distinctive identity for creating a positive image and a favorable reputation for the project.

4.1.1 SENSE4US website

SENSE4US website was created in M1 of the project. The project’s website is a major means of information for and communication with the visitors and thus it is harmonized and interrelated with the main goals of the WP8 to disseminate the project findings as well as to engage key stakeholders for knowledge sharing.

The website is a versatile and resourceful dissemination tool. It is necessary since all the information pertaining to the project is presented there for all audiences. Since the launch of the website, was regularly updated so to attract new and returning visitors. Updates were referred to the project news, project in the press, events, relevant articles, press releases, newsletter issues, synergies and other activities dedicated to dissemination.

The update of the website content, layout and design was conducted throughout the implementation of the project.

Data retrieved from the back end of SENSE4US website show the following:

<i>Field</i>	<i>Data</i>
Newsletter subscribers	86
Number of items on Project News	25
Number of items on Blog	132

Table 4 : Project website data

Data retrieved from Google Analytics for the period 1st October 2015 to 27th December 2016 indicate that the website was visited by 3,339 users. In total there have been 4,671 Sessions and 11,090 Pageviews. Out of the 100% visits, 71.2% were New Visits while 28.8% were Returning Visits and the average visit duration was 2min and 09 sec.

<i>Field</i>	<i>Data</i>
Users	3,339
Number of Sessions	4,671
Number of pageviews	11,090
Number of New Visits	3,325
Number of Returning Visits	1,346
New Visits vs. Returning Visits	71.2% vs. 28.8%

Table 5 : Website data from Google analytics (October 2015 – December 2016)

Furthermore, a number of activities related to the website were performed during the reporting period:

- Queries, expressions of interest and requests with reference to the project are received through the website proving interest for SENSE4US. Responses and/or actions to emails and inquiries are provided by the dissemination and communication team.
- Promotional materials, approved deliverables and papers/publications written by partners are uploaded in the public website and partners’ repository.

4.1.2 SENSE4US Social Media

Social media profiles have played a promotional role for the project, allowing to gain visibility among a wide range of audience.

Regular posts and updates of status on project’s social media profiles on the project developments, news and as sharing of best practices have increased the engagement of the interested audience and helped to achieve interaction with the users.

Social media have been identified as an effective dissemination tool due to its popularity, ease of access and rapid information flow. For this reason, they assist those that use them in order to create an even wider community of interest and disseminate news, activities and developments.

During the reporting period (M25-M39), all project social media profiles were updated on a regular basis with project news as well as other important news that were relevant to the project’s thematic area. Project partners were always invited to share news items with the dissemination team so that these items could be posted on Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn.

The following tables present the status of the social media profiles measured on 27th December of 2016:

<i>Field</i>	<i>Details</i>
Social Network	Facebook
Project Month	September 2015

URL	https://www.facebook.com/pages/SENSE4US-project/562585490456097?ref=hl
Status	124 Likes (45.8% increase in comparison to Y2)

Table 6 : Sense4us page on Facebook (last update December 2016)

Field	Details
Social Network	Twitter
Project Month	September 2015
URL	https://twitter.com/sense4usproject
Status	628 followers (37.1 % increase in comparison to Y2), 3.054 Tweets

Table 7 : SENSE4US profile on Twitter (last update December 2016)

Field	Details
Social Network	LinkedIn
Project Month	September 2015
URL	https://www.linkedin.com/profile/view?trk=nav_responsive_tab_profile&id=286142319
Status	469 connections (22.7% decrease in comparison to Y2)

Table 8 : SENSE4US profile on LinkedIn (last update December 2016)

4.1.2.1 Facebook Page Insights – Twitter Profile Overview

“Facebook Page Insights” is a free service for all Facebook Pages and Facebook Platform application and websites. Facebook Insights provides Facebook Page owners and Facebook Platform developers with metrics about their content. By understanding and analyzing trends within user growth and demographics, consumption of content, and creation of content, Page owners and Platform developers are better equipped to improve their business with Facebook. Only Page administrators, application owners, and domain administrators can view Insights data for the properties they own or administer. The metrics data is aggregated on a daily basis and is made available within 24 hours after a full day is complete.

The figures that can be found in Appendix III show the overall data of the Facebook Page Insights for SENSE4US Facebook profile for the reporting period of October 2015 to December 2016. In the Appendix III, data on “Number of people the posts reached”, “Total Page Likes”, as well as the post that most people reached within the reporting period, etc. can be found.

The overview of Twitter profile is provided by the free tool Hootsuite. This tool is a Social Media Management System that helps its users to keep track and manage their social network channels. Multiple networks such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Google+ can be managed at the same time. Moreover it provides Analytic tools for users’ profiles. In this

deliverable we used the Hootsuite tool in order to efficiently measure the project’s Twitter presence. In the Appendix IV, data on “Followers growth”, “Most popular links” as well as SENSE4US profile summary for the reporting period can be found.

4.1.3 Newsletter

As already mentioned in D8.4 Dissemination Plan (M6), the project newsletters are used to announce the project, develop a profile, give regular updates on its progress and developments and achieve buy-in and take-up of its solution after the completion of the project. The newsletters are creative dissemination tools addressing them to target audiences to know that the project is a success.

During the reporting period (M25-39), three newsletter issues have been published in February 2016, May 2016 and December 2016. Due to the 3 month extension of SENSE4US lifetime, the Newsletter Issue No.10 was released in December 2016 (M39) and not in September 2016 (M36) as mentioned in D8.4 Dissemination Plan.

Each newsletter issue was focused on updating about the latest project news, the events in which partners participated as well as other interesting news and publications that worth mentioning, while they suggest events related to the project’s field of activity to all readers. Thus, the newsletter’s structure consists of the following standard sections: “Editorial”, “Project News”, “Interesting news”, “Upcoming Events” and “Publications”.

The newsletter issues are accessible in the “Newsletter” section of the website (<http://www.sense4us.eu/index.php/news-letter>), in which the visitor or user can easily subscribe to the newsletter distribution list and follow the project’s progress on a quarterly basis. In Y3, the following SENSE4US Newsletter Issues have been released:

<i>Issue</i>	<i>Date of release</i>	<i>Available in URL</i>
Newsletter Issue No.8	February 2016	http://www.sense4us.eu/index.php/news-letter/28-newsletter/152-issue-no-8-february-2016
Newsletter Issue No.9	May 2016	http://www.sense4us.eu/index.php/news-letter?id=222
Newsletter Issue No.10	December 2016	http://www.sense4us.eu/index.php/news-letter

Table 9 : Newsletter Issues

4.1.4 Press Release

Apart from the project website, a press release is considered the second most efficient tool for the dissemination of the project since its distribution to a large number of recipients (media, EC contacts, eGovernment communities and networks, stakeholder groups etc.) helps promote the project at national, European and international level. Press releases will be produced throughout the project on the purpose of media engagement in the dissemination of the project's development and achievements.

It has been decided within WP8 that collaboration of the other project partners translate the press release in their native language level. Gov2u has also created and shared with the partners the document "Media Guidelines for press focal points on the purpose of explaining

the procedure that the press focal points have to follow to achieve the proper dissemination and wider promotion of the press releases.

At national and local level, the press releases were sent by each press focal point to a media list created for this reason in order to raise awareness and visibility of the project and its development throughout its duration. The press releases are also uploaded on the website, posted on its social media profiles as well as on Joinup portal. Finally, the media coverage of the press releases is regularly monitored by Gov2u and the press focal points so it is possible to estimate the impact in the public.

<i>Final Press Release</i>	<i>Details</i>
Partner responsible	Gov2u
Title	“SENSE4US Project completes lifecycle”
URL	http://www.sense4us.eu/index.php/project-news/283-final-press-release-sense4us-project-completes-lifecycle
Date of release	28/12/16
Other information	The PR announces the end of lifecycle of SENSE4US project as well as the outcomes of the final conference in Brussels.

Table 10 : Press Release

4.1.5 Promotional materials

During Y3, the following project marketing materials were created by Gov2u and uploaded on the project website:

- [Updated project brochure](#)
- [Flyer](#)
- [Brussels conference invitation](#)
- [Conference poster](#)

These materials comprise a collection of dissemination and promotional tools that were used to support the project’s identity, to raise its awareness and visibility, to attract and motivate stakeholders, although they are in electronic version.

The project coordinator, ITI, created a [video](#) based on the “coasting schools” case study for the Brussels event (8th December 2016), designed a flyer for the London event (12th July 2016), created a presentation as a summary of a case study for the London event (12th July 2016).

Moreover, Hansard society created for Brussels event (8th December 2016) the following promotional material: Agenda, Speaker bios, Sense4us information pack, EU conference poster (Copyrights), EU conference poster (Policy modelling), EU conference poster (Senti circles), EU conference poster (Text index analysis), EU conference poster (LOD.)

The promotional materials are described in detail in D8.3 submitted in December 2016 (M39).

4.2 Dissemination and communication activities

The following sections outline the dissemination activities carried out during this reporting period:

4.2.1 Organization of events

A strong dissemination activity for partners is to organize dedicated events at local or national level, similar to “Info Days” or “Focus Groups”, in order to disseminate the project among various interested stakeholders. The following events have been organized by the consortium partners in collaboration with other third parties:

<i>Partner/s</i>	<i>Name of event</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Venue/Location</i>	<i>Description of event</i>	<i>Type of audience</i>	<i>Results and outcomes</i>
HS co-organized with SU, Gov2u, Gesis, KMi, ITI, UKOB)	"Policy Making in a Complex World"	Thursday 8 December 2016 (9am-17pm)	The Sofitel Hotel, Brussels	SENSE4Us Conference Policy Making in a Complex World - Can new technologies help us better understand, engage and build the trust of citizens?	EU Commission, UK Policy Makers, Academics, Start ups, NGOs and Civic Society Organisations	How new technologies can help support our democracy, revealing a novel path for the future of decision-making. The stakeholders were informed about how digital tools and technologies can enable policy makers' access and summarize a wide array of relevant data, taking into account the views of citizens on policy issues and better acknowledging the implications of proposed policies.
Hansard Society	Future Parliament: Hacking the legislative process//capacity, scrutiny, engagement	14 Nov 2016 (2pm-6pm)	Westminster Central Hall, London, UK	This event, explored the problems in the legislative process – e.g. time, speed, resources, access to expert knowledge, scrutiny capacity – and how new	The opening event of the UK Parliament's 'Parliament Week' (a programme of events and activities to connect people	The Sense4us project was introduced at the start of the event, and the tools were showcased during it. Live demonstratio

			<p>technological developments might help solve them. With the UK Parliament expected to move to a temporary new location in a few years to facilitate a major refurbishment programme, a second panel explored how a temporary new building could be turned into a parliamentary laboratory to trial and test new digital technology to support the legislative and scrutiny process.</p> <p>Web links:</p> <p>Video of the event panels:</p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLchplkwdUkzbN3Dm6wVmlxoNj5X-k3H-Q</p> <p>Hansard Society Despatch Box Blogposts:</p> <p>‘You can look but don’t touch: Making the legislative process more accessible’ (http://blog.hansardsociety.org.uk/you-can-look-but-dont-touch-making-the-legislative-process-more-accessible/)</p> <p>‘Culture, design and filter bubbles: looking back at #Future Parliament’ (http://blog.hansardsociety.org.uk/culture-design-</p>	<p>across the UK with Parliament and democracy), this event brought together around 80 experts from Parliament, the technology sectors and civil society, including MPs, parliamentary clerks from Westminster, the Scottish Parliament, National Assembly for Wales and Northern Ireland Assembly, journalists (including BBC Parliament), and civil society/political reform campaign groups.</p> <p>Speakers were: Emma Allen, Director of Digital Development, Parliamentary Digital Service</p> <p>Victoria Boelman, Principal Researcher in Government Innovation, Nesta</p> <p>Stella Creasy MP, Labour MP for Walthamstow, Member of the House of Commons Science and</p>	<p>ns of the tools were run by project partners and videos explaining the project were screened during the breaks.</p> <p>The event assisted with end user engagement; several organisations expressed interest in the future of the tools and further meetings to discuss them were organised as a result</p>
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D8.7 Final Dissemination Report

				<p>and-filter-bubbles-looking-back-at-futureparliament/)</p> <p>Selection of photographs: Flickr https://www.flickr.com/photos/hansardsociety/albums/72157660800237778</p>	<p>Technology Select Committee.</p> <p>Dr Ruth Fox, Director and Head of Research, Hansard Society (Sense4us project)</p> <p>Elizabeth Linder, Founder and CEO of The Conversational Century and former Government and Politics Specialist, Facebook.</p> <p>Liam Laurence Smyth, Clerk of Legislation, House of Commons</p> <p>Rebecca Rumbul, Head of Research, mySociety</p> <p>Bill Thompson, Partnership Lead, Make it Digital, BBC and freelance journalist, commentator and technology critic.</p> <p>Paul Walland, Innovation Director at IT Innovation Centre, University of Southampton (Sense4us)</p>	
Stockholm University	CISMOB Intelligent Transport	16 Sept. 2016	Stockholm, Sweden	CISMOB main vision is to promote innovative ways to reduce carbon	Elected representatives, government officials,	Cross Project Collaboration – Sense4us was presented to

Conference			footprint and increase the sustainability of urban areas by improving the efficiency in the use of urban transport infrastructure through ICT. In a context of increasing availability of sensor technology to monitor and record large amounts of data, a common challenge to policy makers is to identify the best practices to take advantage of these new sources of data and use them to prioritize intervention areas, to manage efficiently current road networks, to inform citizens and motivate them to choose more sustainable mobility options. http://egovlab.eu/cismob/	media, political parties, academics and corporate representatives in the field of ITS	the group of Interreg EU partners in a dedicated workshop during the event.
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Table 11 : Organization of events

4.2.2 Participation in conferences, workshops and events

One of the key activities for the promotion of the project’s objectives and developments is the participation in events, workshops and conferences. In these events, presentations were performed by consortium partners showcasing the project and provided the most essential updates to interested stakeholders on project’s progress. The events at local and EU level were mainly related to Open Data, Modelling, Policy Making, etc.

Appendix I of the current document includes all the events and conferences that partners participated during the reporting period (M25-M39) of the project.

4.2.3 Articles, publications, papers (accepted/submitted/presented to conference proceedings and scientific journals)

According to the DoW it is foreseen that “papers, articles and other publications related to the project will be prepared with the cooperation of project partners and submitted in relevant conferences and journals focused on ICT R&D, eGovernment, eParticipation etc., in order to promote the project in national, European and international promotion level”.

It is important to mention that in Y1 of SENSE4US project 14 papers were written and accepted, while in Y2 there are 18 papers produced in total. In Y3, 5 papers have been published, 6 papers has been submitted and pending review, while 2 papers have been accepted and will be published soon. The papers that have been written (published, accepted and under review) are listed below:

Field	Details
Title of publication	From Assumptions to Artifacts: Unfolding e-Participation within Public Sector Redesign
Date of publication	2017
Name of the author	Joshi, S., When, U.
Published/presented at	International Journal of Electronic Governance
Status	Accepted
Abstract	The belief that using vast bodies of open data via e-Participation can generate dramatic transformation in public sector redesign and result in societal benefits – is heralded as a shift towards public innovation. It is precisely this belief that we examine in this paper. We start our investigation by providing a conceptualization of what participation means within the context of open data. By using a cross case comparison, of two European research projects, we provide an empirical base upon which we can examine the process of participation – both as a political construct and as technological design.

Table 12 : From Assumptions to Artifacts: Unfolding e-Participation within Public Sector Redesign

Field	Details
Title of publication	Multi-stakeholder Preference Analysis in Ex-ante Evaluation of Policy Options - Use Case: Ultra Low Emission Vehicles in UK
Date of publication	5th - 8th Sep. 2016
Name of the author	Anton Talantsev, Osama Ibrahim and Aron Larsson
Published/presented at	Dual EGOV 2016 and ePart 2016 conference – home 15th IFIP Electronic Government (EGOV) and 8th Electronic Participation (ePart) Conference 2016 United Nations University Operating Unit on Policy-Driven Electronic Governance (UNU-EGOV) and University of Minho. Guimarães, Portugal

Status	Accepted
Abstract	This study reviews multi-attribute decision-making (MADM) technique and presents a common policy appraisal format using main evaluation criteria linked to a set of measurable, context dependent attributes. We argue for a rank-based approach for eliciting preferences, select a novel method for attribute weight elicitation, and show how it can be integrated within a public policy multi-criteria evaluation framework. A use case for policymaking, ‘Ultra-Low Emission Vehicles (ULEV) Uptake in UK’, is used for demonstration of the proposed approach for policy decision analysis. This approach seeks to couple systems modelling and simulation of policy scenarios with MCDA, stakeholder analysis and preference elicitation.
URL	http://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-45074-2_14

Table 13 : Multi-stakeholder Preference Analysis in Ex-ante Evaluation of Policy Options - Use Case: Ultra Low Emission Vehicles in UK

Field	Details
Title of publication	Labelled Causal Mapping for Modelling and Simulation of Policy Options
Date of publication	To be published 2017
Name of the author	Osama Ibrahim and Aron Larsson
Published/presented at	International Journal of Electronic Governance (IJEG) – Inderscience. http://www.inderscience.com/ijeg
Status	Peer reviewed
Abstract	This paper presents a new tool for systemic modelling and simulation of public policy problems. The tool bridges the gap between the user’s complex mental model and the explicit graphical representation in order to enable knowledge representation and system analysis. It allows users to build a systems model of a policy decision situation and simulate the system behaviour and responses to changing external factors and policy interventions over time. We propose a policy-oriented problem structuring method, Labelled causal mapping, which provides a labelling scheme with iconic representation of the involved actors and key variables and a quantitative dynamic simulation model of the control flows and causal dependencies.

Table 14 : Labelled Causal Mapping for Modelling and Simulation of Policy Options

Field	Details
Title of publication	Fossil-free Public Transport: Prescriptive Policy Analysis for the Swedish Bus Fleets
Date of publication	6 – 9 Jun. 2016

Name of the author	Maria Xylia, Osama Ibrahim and Semida Silveira.
Published/presented at	13th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM), Porto, Portugal. http://eem2016.com/
Status	Accepted
Abstract	This study presents a prescriptive policy analysis for the “fossil-free fuel deployment for public transport buses at the national level in Sweden”, using a policy-oriented modelling and simulation tool, Sense4us1, that supports systems analysis for policy involving: (i) Structuring of policy problems using the labelled causal mapping method, (ii) Ex ante Impact assessment using scenario-based dynamic simulation modelling and (iii) Ex-ante evaluation of the considered policy options based on the simulation results and using a set of standard criteria for evaluation of EU policy interventions.
URL	http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?tp=&arnumber=7521266&isnumber=7521173

Table 15 : Fossil-free Public Transport: Prescriptive Policy Analysis for the Swedish Bus Fleets

<i>Field</i>	<i>Details</i>
Title of publication	Who gains and who loses in the shift to electric vehicles: impact assessment through multi-criteria multi-stakeholder analysis
Date of publication	12 - 14 Oct. 2016
Name of the author	Anton Talantsev
Published/presented at	The international conference: “Green Urbanism”, Rome, Italy
Status	Accepted
Abstract	Studying the case of the subsidy for electric vehicles in Great Britain (“plug-in car grant”), this research suggests an integrated impact assessment approach by coupling policy issue system modeling with stakeholder preference elicitation. In particular, we utilize fuzzy cognitive mapping to model the policy issue as a dynamic and complex system. We further simulate the subsidy policy in the model to estimate the changes in select policy aspects. The simulation outcomes are assessed through perspectives of stakeholder groups. For the latter task, nine stakeholder groups were identified and profiled by conducting content analysis and applying the novel CAR method.

Table 16 : Who gains and who loses in the shift to electric vehicles: impact assessment through multi-criteria multi-stakeholder analysis

<i>Field</i>	<i>Details</i>
Title of publication	Hassan Saif, Miriam Fernandez, Leon Kastler, Harith Alani “A Linked Open Data Approach for Sentiment Lexicon Adaptation”, Proceedings of the Fourth International Workshop on Linked Data for Information Extraction co-located with 15th International

	Semantic Web Conference (ISWC 2016), October 18, 2016 pp. 11-22
Date of publication	October 18, 2016
Name of the author	Hassan Saif, Miriam Fernandez, Leon Kastler, Harith Alani,
Published/presented at	Fourth International Workshop on Linked Data for Information Extraction co-located with 15th International Semantic Web Conference (http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-1699/)
Status	Under revision
Abstract	The goal of the paper was the adaption sentiment dictionaries for social media data. One part focussed on the adaption according semantic relations. First, we identified entities within tweets, captured relations between these entities and adapted the dictionary accordingly.
URL	http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-1699/paper-03.pdf

Table 17 : A Linked Open Data Approach for Sentiment Lexicon Adaptation

<i>Field</i>	<i>Details</i>
Title of publication	Hassan Saif, Miriam Fernandez, Leon Kastler, Thomas Dickinson and Harith Alani "A Semantic Graph-based Approach for Detecting pro-ISIS Stances on", H. Saif, T. Dickinson, L. Kastler, M. Fernandez, H.Alani. A Semantic Graph-based Approach for Radicalisation Detection on Social Media. Submitted to ESWC 2017
Date of publication	n/a
Name of the author	Hassan Saif, Miriam Fernandez, Leon Kastler, Thomas Dickinson and Harith Alani
Published/presented at	ISWC 2017
Status	Under revision
Abstract	Automated identification of pro-isis and anit-isis twitter user based on sub-graph patterns in semantic relation graphs of entities used in users' tweets

Table 18 : A Semantic Graph-based Approach for Detecting pro-ISIS Stances on

<i>Field</i>	<i>Details</i>
Title of publication	Cristina Sarasua, Matthias Thimm, Steffen Staab. Methods for

	Intrinsic Evaluation of Links in the Web of Data.
Date of publication	n/a
Name of the author	Cristina Sarasua, Matthias Thimm, Steffen Staab
Published/presented at	ISWC 2017
Status	Under revision
Abstract	Development of link assessment methods. Analyse of over 1 million links from 35 relevant data sets of the Linked Open Data Cloud, in order to observe the adoption of core data integration principles.

Table 19 : Methods for Intrinsic Evaluation of Links in the Web of Data

<i>Field</i>	<i>Details</i>
Title of publication	Contextual semantics for sentiment analysis of Twitter
Date of publication	2016
Name of the author	Hasan Saif
Published/presented at	Information Processing & Management 52.1 (2016): 5-19.
Status	Under Revision
Abstract	Sentiment analysis on Twitter has attracted much attention recently due to its wide applications in both, commercial and public sectors. In this paper we present SentiCircles, a lexicon-based approach for sentiment analysis on Twitter. Different from typical lexicon-based approaches, which offer a fixed and static prior sentiment polarities of words regardless of their context, SentiCircles takes into account the co-occurrence patterns of words in different contexts in tweets to capture their semantics and update their pre-assigned strength and polarity in sentiment lexicons accordingly. Our approach allows for the detection of sentiment at both entity-level and tweet-level. We evaluate our proposed approach on three Twitter datasets using three different sentiment lexicons to derive word prior sentiments. Results show that our approach significantly outperforms the baselines in accuracy and <i>F</i> -measure for entity-level subjectivity (neutral vs. polar) and polarity (positive vs. negative) detections. For tweet-level sentiment detection, our approach performs better than the state-of-the-art SentiStrength by 4–5% in accuracy in two datasets, but falls marginally behind by 1% in <i>F</i> -measure in the third dataset.

Table 20 : Contextual semantics for sentiment analysis of Twitter

<i>Field</i>	<i>Details</i>
Title of publication	Sentiment Lexicon Adaptation with Context and Semantics for the Social Web
Date of publication	28 July 2016
Name of the author	H. Saif, M. Fernandez, L. Kastler, H.Alani.
Published/presented at	Semantic Web Journal. Special Issue: Mining Social Semantics on the Social Web.
Status	Accepted
Abstract	<p>Sentiment analysis over social streams offers governments and organisations a fast and effective way to monitor the publics' feelings towards policies, brands, business, etc. General purpose sentiment lexicons have been used to compute sentiment from social streams, since they are simple and effective. They calculate the overall sentiment of texts by using a general collection of words, with predetermined sentiment orientation and strength. However, words' sentiment often vary with the contexts in which they appear, and new words might be encountered that are not covered by the lexicon, particularly in social media environments where content emerges and changes rapidly and constantly. In this paper, we propose a lexicon adaptation approach that uses contextual as well as semantic information extracted from DBpedia to update the words' weighted sentiment orientations and to add new words to the lexicon. We evaluate our approach on three different Twitter datasets, and show that enriching the lexicon with contextual and semantic information improves sentiment computation by 3.4% in average accuracy, and by 2.8% in average F1 measure.</p>
URL	http://www.semantic-web-journal.net/content/sentiment-lexicon-adaptation-context-and-semantics-social-web-0

Table 21 : Sentiment Lexicon Adaptation with Context and Semantics for the Social Web.

<i>Field</i>	<i>Details</i>
Title of publication	SentiCircles: A Platform for Contextual and Conceptual Sentiment Analysis
Date of publication	20 October 2016
Name of the author	H.Saif, M. Bashevoy, S. Taylor, M.Fernandez, H. Alani.
Published presented at	Demo paper at ESWC2016.
Status	Accepted
Abstract	<p>Sentiment analysis over social streams offers governments and organisations a fast and effective way to monitor the publics'</p>

	feelings towards policies, brands, business, etc. In this paper we present SentiCircles, a platform that captures feedback from social media conversations and applies contextual and conceptual sentiment analysis models to extract and summarise sentiment from these conversations. It provides a novel sentiment navigation design where contextual sentiment is captured and presented at term/entity level, enabling a better alignment of positive and negative sentiment to the nature of the public debate.
URL	http://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-47602-5_28

Table 22 : SentiCircles: A Platform for Contextual and Conceptual Sentiment Analysis

Field	Details
Title of publication	Pro-Environmental Campaigns via Social Media: Analysing Awareness and Behaviour Patterns
Date of publication	n/a
Name of the author	M. Fernandez
Published presented at	Web Science Journal
Status	Under Revision
Abstract	n/a

Table 23 : Pro-Environmental Campaigns via Social Media: Analysing Awareness and Behaviour Patterns

Field	Details
Title of publication	A Semantic Graph-based Approach for Radicalisation Detection on Social Media.
Date of publication	n/a
Name of the author	H. Saif, T. Dickinson, L. Kastler, M. Fernandez, H.Alani.
Published presented at	Submitted to ESWC 2017
Status	Under revision
Abstract	n/a

Table 24 : A Semantic Graph-based Approach for Radicalisation Detection on Social Media.

4.2.4 Contact with stakeholders

As in Y1 and Y2 of project's implementation, also in Y3 partners entered into engagement with the project stakeholders in a spirit of respect and openness that would facilitate the communication and contact with the groups of people that interest our project.

Gov2u has send an invitation for Brussels Final Conference to 600 contacts in pan-European level on 2nd December in order to raise the visibility of the event and attract more participants

Partners' interaction during the reporting period is being presented in the table below:

<i>Partner and contact</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Venue / Location</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Stockholm Unoversity and Lantmäteriet	29th Nov. 2016	Gävle, Sweden	The Swedish Land Survey Organisation invited us to present the Sense4us project and the tool for modelling and simulation more precisely. Since the land survey organisation deals with vast bodies of open & expert data – they were very appreciative of a tool that enabled them to map causal relations between variables and chart the complexity of the data they hold. The event was a half day workshop.
GESIS	23rd Nov. – 10th Dec. 2016	North-Rhine Westphalia	Hands-on trails at German Bundestag, at Parliament in NRW, in municipalities and with people from lobby groups and federal offices (Insightful live tests, based on assigned tasks and free navigation within the toolbox respectively within the tools, final evaluation of the latest updated toolbox; assessment by end users has been done in many ways: UI, each tool, integration of different tools, many valuable ideas, references, inspirations and criticism has fed in)
GESIS	14 Sep. 2016	North-Rhine Westphalia	Face-to-face interviews at regional level: Parliament with MPs and their assistants; to test/evaluate the guidance and FAQ as well as the present toolbox version(User-based test examples linked to their area of interest / policy issues, presentation in flexible manner, screenshots and concepts of the tools , helpful feedback to improve the toolbox itself as well as the guidance and FAQ)
Stockholm Unoversity and Dr. Leena Ilmola-Sheppard, Senior researcher, Advanced Systems Analysis Program, International Institute for applied systems Analysis	August 2016	Laxenburg, Austria	A research study on Finland's immigration crisis, a policy analysis using the Sense4us policy modelling and simulation tool, based on a unique dataset generated through expert workshops facilitated by Dr. Leena Ilmola-Sheppard for evaluation of the tool.
Stockholm Unoversity and Training the Trainers	21st June,	Stockholm, Sweden	SENSE4US end user partners had a really useful training workshop in Stockholm on June 21st, to enable and equip them with the methods/tools for future end user

Workshop	2016		<p>engagement workshops</p> <p>A bit before the final version of the toolkit is released, end user partners were gathered to ascertain a better understanding of how the tool works and its potential value.</p> <p>As a result of their joint efforts, a number of suggestions for useful improvements emerged that would make the tool much more accessible and useful to end users.</p>
Stockholm University and James Salisi, Health policy researcher, Karolinska Institute	During Spring Semester 2016	Stockholm, Sweden	<p>As a topic for James' Master thesis in Health informatics, we have done a study to demonstrate problem structuring and simulation of consequences of a health policy issue, 'the problem of childhood obesity in the UK'; to perform usability evaluation of the prototype tool; and to recommend improvement in the user interface of the prototype tool in general and for health policy researchers/analyst in particular.</p>
Stockholm University and Naturvårdsverket (Swedish EPA)	10-11 March 2016	Stockholm, Sweden	<p>Sense4us project as a whole and more specifically the modelling and simulation tool for policy analysts was presented at the event. Here we received excellent feedback from stakeholders, namely the EPA policy analysts who saw great potential in the application of the tool to their everyday research activities. The event was a full two day conference</p> <p>https://www.naturvardsverket.se/upload/kalendarium/2016/open-data/naturvardsverket-open-data-next-steps-final-agenda.pdf</p>
Stockholm University and Maria Xylia, Energy policy researcher, Energy and Climate Studies Unit, Department of Energy Technology, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm, Sweden	14-17 Sep. 2015 1st Dec. 2015	Stockholm, Sweden	<p>Nordic PhD course in Advanced Systems Analysis: economic, technical and societal aspects</p> <p>Working on a policy analysis case using the Sense4us policy modelling and simulation tool. "fossil-free fuel deployment for public transport buses at the national level in Sweden". We published a paper together at the European energy Market Conference EEM2016.</p>

Table 25 : Contact with stakeholders

4.2.5 Press coverage

In this section news articles or references to the project are being presented for both national and European levels:

Partner	Title	Date	Media	URL
Hansard Society	Can technology improve our democracy?	13 December 2016	IT Pro	http://www.itpro.co.uk/government-it-strategy/27775/can-technology-improve-our-democracy

Hansard Society	Technology: the cause of and solution to democracy's problems?	9 December 2016	Alphr News	http://www.alphr.com/politics/1004938/technology-the-cause-of-and-solution-to-democracy-s-problems
Hansard Society	Future Parliament: How a change of scenery could encourage innovation	16 November 2016	Public Technology	https://www.publictechnology.net/articles/features/future-parliament-how-change-scenery-could-encourage-innovation
Gov2u	SENSE4US project releases its No.9 newsletter issue!	2nd June 2016	Joinup portal	https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/news/sense4us-project-releases-its-no9-newsletter-issue
Gov2u	Press Release	29th December 2016	Joinup portal	https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/news/sense4us-project-completes-lifecycle-final-press-release
Gov2u	SENSE4US project releases its No.10 newsletter issue!	29th December 2016	Joinup portal	https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/news/sense4us-project-releases-its-no10-newsletter-issue

Table 26 : Press coverage

4.2.6 Liaison with other projects, networks & initiatives

Effective networking is about building strong and useful relationships and liaisons over time that can lead to mutual understanding, trust, acceptance and benefits with similar EU projects and other networks and initiatives. Such liaisons and networks can help in our effort to raise the project's positive reputation and take-up of its solution in the long term.

During the reporting period, the effort to approach and collaborate with other projects and networks continued and some progress was made.

4.2.6.1 Contact with other European projects

During the reporting period, in the context of the continuation of efforts to collaborate with other projects related to similar thematic areas with SENSE4US, Gov2u introduced the project by email and asked for further collaboration with the following projects:

- **INSIGHT** : Innovative Policy Modelling and Governance Tools for Sustainable Post-Crisis Urban Development (*7th Framework Programme*)
- **Simpol**: Financial Systems SIMulation and POLicy Modelling (*7th Framework Programme*)

- **SYMPHONY** : Orchestrating Information Technologies and Global Systems Science for Policy Design and Regulation of a Resilient and Sustainable Global Economy (*7th Framework Programme*)
- **Policy Compass** (*7th Framework Programme*)
- **GROWTHCOM** - Growth and innovation policy-modelling: applying next generation tools, data, and economic complexity ideas (*7th Framework Programme*)
- **PHEME** : Computing Veracity Across Media, Languages, and Social Networks (*7th Framework Programme*)
- **SAM**: Dynamic Social and Media Content Syndication for 2nd Screen. (*7th Framework Programme*)
- **REVEAL**: REVEALing hidden concepts in Social Media (*7th Framework Programme*)
- **ECSM**: European Centre for Social Media
- **EUMSSI**: Event Understanding through Multimodal Social Stream Interpretation (*7th Framework Programme*)
- **USEMP**: User Empowerment for Enhanced Online Presence Management (*7th Framework Programme*)
- **HUMANE**: a typology, method and roadmap for HUman-MAchine Networks (*Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme*).
- **InVID**: In Video Veritas: Verification of Social Media Video Content for the News Industry (*Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme*).
- **SocialSensor** : Sensing User Generated Input for Improved Media Discovery and Experience (*7th Framework Programme*)
- **Newsreader** : Building structured event Indexes of large volumes of financial and economic Data for Decision Making (*7th Framework Programme*)
- **CoeGSS**: Center of Excellence for Global Systems Science (*Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme*).

From the aforementioned projects, they have agreed for collaborating with SENSE4US project the following EU projects:

<i>EU Project</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>URL</i>
EUMSSI	EUMSSI develops technologies for identifying and aggregating data presented as unstructured information in sources of very different nature (video, audio, text and social context), including both online (e.g. YouTube) and traditional media (e.g. audiovisual repositories), and for dealing	www.eumssi.eu

	with information of very different degrees of granularity.	
European Centre for Social Media (ECSM)	European Centre for Social Media (ECSM) is a forum supporting the organisation of social media technologic and marketing activities, training and dissemination venues. Areas covered involve social media analytics, verification, visualization and their applications, e.g. in news, marketing, e-gov, e-participation, and more.	http://www.socialmediacentre.eu/
Policy Compass	The main goal of Policy Compass is to develop a research prototype of an easy-to-use, highly visual and intuitive tool for social networks and eParticipation platforms, enabling citizens and public officials to easily create, apply, share, embed, annotate and discuss causal models, charts and graphs of historical data from trusted open data sources. The aim is to develop methods and tools that facilitate more factual, evidence-based, transparent and accountable policy evaluation and analysis.	www.policycompass.eu
Reveal	REVEAL aims to advance the necessary technologies for making a higher level analysis of social media possible. The project is developing tools and services that aid in Social Media verification, particularly from the journalistic and enterprise perspective. The main objective is to discover higher level concepts hidden within social media information and thus enable users to reveal hidden 'modalities' such as reputation, influence or credibility of information.	www.revealproject.eu
Step	STEP is an EU funded project that aims to promote the societal and political participation of young people in decision making procedures on environmental issues. For this, STEP develops and pilot tests a cloud eParticipation SaaS platform, enhanced with web / social media mining, gamification, machine translation, and visualisation features to facilitate the better interaction between young people and policy makers	www.step4youth.eu

CoeGSS	CoeGSS project aims at empowering the community of analysts addressing global challenges through high-performance computing and data analysis. In particular, the project will develop an HPC-based framework to generate synthetic information systems for tackling global challenges	http://coegss.eu
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Table 27 : EU similar projects

4.2.6.2 Collaboration with other projects and organizations

During the reporting period project partners have approach projects and organizations for further cooperation actions with SENSE4US project. On the following table these activities are described:

<i>Partner</i>	<i>Project Name</i>	<i>Contact person or Organization</i>	<i>Description of cooperation activity</i>
Hansard Society	Parliamentary Office of Science and Technology (POST): Research Study Steering Group	Dr Caroline Kenny, Social Science Adviser, POST	As a member of the Steering Group (an appointment arising from engagement with POST during year 1 end user engagement on the Sense4us project), Ruth Fox has met with POST staff on several occasions to discuss mutual areas of interest about the legislative process and use of technology, and reviews/comments on the draft reports of POST’s study of how research is used by the UK Parliament. The final report will be published some time in 2017.
UKOB	Koldfish	Leon Kastler, Institute for Web Science and Technologies	The Koldfish project's aims to improve the life of linked open data users by offering services and methods to access, explore, and utilize LOD in a simpler and more convenient fashion. Several methods and

			<p>implementations of the Sense4us LOD search have been applied in Koldfish e.g. both need to access linked open data and identify URIs suitable for a user's request.</p> <p>(see also: http://west.uni-koblenz.de/en/research/koldfish)</p>
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Table 28 : Collaboration with other project and organizations

4.2.6.3 JoinUp

Joinup is a collaborative platform created by the European Commission and funded by the European Union via the Interoperability Solutions for Public Administrations¹ (ISA) Programme. It offers several services that aim to help e-Government professionals share their experience with each other and also hopes to support them to find, choose, re-use, develop and implement interoperability solutions. We continue using the platform to disseminate project news (press release, newsletters, marketing material, etc.) and to reach great audiences at pan-European level.

4.2.6.4 E.N.T.E.R network

E.N.T.E.R Network (www.enter-network.eu) for Transfer and Exploitation of EU project results aims to support EU strategies through the dissemination and exploitation of project results. Apart from giving project coordinators the opportunity to disseminate information about project and their results to a broad community of interested organizations and bodies, it also gives European citizens and organizations the opportunity to receive information regularly about results in the EU project community. Through the E.N.T.E.R. network, we have disseminated our dissemination materials and it is a valuable source of information and project promotion as a total number of more than 889 Members and 521 Projects.

4.2.7 Overview of dissemination tools and activities

The following table summarizes the aforementioned dissemination tools utilized and the activities performed during the reporting period. The tools and activities and their results are grouped in categories with similar characteristics, so that their overall potential is stressed.

Type of activity	Number
Papers, article presentations	13

¹ <http://ec.europa.eu/isa/>

Organization of and participation in events, workshops, conferences	12
Newsletter Issues	3
Project Presentation	2
Press Coverage	6

Table 29 : Overview of dissemination tools and activities

5 Conclusions

According to the DoW, the principal objective of this deliverable was to present an update of D8.6 describing all the dissemination tools used and activities implemented to disseminate the project results for the reporting period M25-M39.

The objectives of the reporting period have been achieved with certain activities performed by all partners and dissemination tools that assisted towards the achievement of these objectives. The second part provides a short summary of the dissemination and communication activities made by project partners during the Y1 and Y2 of project's implementation. The third and fourth part of the deliverable focus on the aforementioned issues giving a detailed report to the reader.

6 References

- [1] http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Executive_summary

APPENDIX I – Events and Conferences

Participation in conferences, workshops and events

Partners	Name of the event	Date	Venue/Location	Description of event	Type of audience	Results and outcomes
Stockholm University	50th ICA Conference	13-16 November 2016	Medellin, Colombia	International Council for IT in Government Administration (ICA) http://www.ica-it.org/index.php/conference-programme-f	CIOs of international governments	Citizens and industry request more control over their own data. Some citizens want OYOD (Own Your Own Data) where others are resisting the virtualization all together. During the session V. Koulolias (eGovlab) lead the discussion and presented the possibilities of how technological tools like Sense4us can lead to new era of “anticipatory governance.” Are co-creation & participatory design - the key to trust & transparency for policy making? What are the big, open & linked data challenges in policy making? The feedback of the break-out group composed of CIOs from over 20 countries and organizations was presented during the report back of the conference session.
Hansard Society	House of Lords Constitution Committee inquiry into the legislative process	2 November 2016	Committee Room 1, House of Lords, Westminster, London, UK	The Hansard Society's director, Dr Ruth Fox gave oral evidence at the first session of the Committee's new inquiry into the legislative process.	12 members of the House of Lords drawn from the Conservative, Labour and Liberal Democrat parties as well as the independent crossbench. See membership list here:	The meeting was recorded and broadcast live on the UK Parliament TV channel. One of the key questions the committee is exploring is what role technology might play in supporting the legislative process. Ruth Fox referenced the Sense4us tools in response to this question. The relevant question starts at about 11:21 in the video. http://www.parliamentlive.tv/Event/Index/2ca542c

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					<p>http://www.parliament.uk/business/committees/committees-a-z/lords-select/constitution-committee/mnis-membership/</p> <p>Sir Richard Mottram, former Permanent Secretary in the civil service, and current Chair of the Better Government Initiative was also present giving evidence.</p>	<p>6-b00d-4f6a-b0ee-e9ab3cd0969f</p> <p>See also the response at Q7 in the transcript:</p> <p>http://data.parliament.uk/writtenevidence/committees-evidence.svc/evidencedocument/constitution-committee/legislative-process/oral/42695.pdf</p>
Stockholm University	Young Scientists Summer Program (YSSP2016) – Research assistantship in the Advanced systems analysis program	1st June – 30th Sept. 2016	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Laxenburg, Austria.	<p>A research program for 51 PhD Students from all over the world. http://www.iiasa.ac.at/web/home/education/yssp/about.html</p> <p>Participant: Osama Ibrahim</p>	Research and Technology audience	Introduction of the Sense4us project – Research study: “Evaluation of the Sense4us policy modelling and simulation tool – Prescriptive policy analysis for Finland’s immigration crisis”
KMi	Miriam Fernandez Invited Talk at the RNSA-IMEDIR Symposium	20th June 2016	La Corunna, Spain	n/a	n/a	n/a
KMi	Miriam Fernandez. Invited Talk at the PhD program UNED University	13th June 2016	Madrid, Spain	n/a	n/a	n/a

KMi	Hassan Saif. Invited Talk at the Semantic Sentiment Analysis Workshop. ESWC 2016.	2016	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
KMi	Hassan Saif. Invited Talk as best thesis award recipient at ISWC 2016	2016	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
KMi	Hassan Saif. Conference Talk presenting "A Linked Open Data Approach for Sentiment Lexicon Adaptation." Linked Data for Information Extraction Workshop at ISWC2016	2016	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
KMi	Hassan Saif. Conference Talk presenting SentiCircles: A Platform for Contextual and Conceptual Sentiment Analysis. Demo paper at ESWC2016.	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a

APPENDIX II – Google Analytics Data

Below you may find the most important data related to the website. The data are mentioned also in section 4.1.1

Figure 1 : Audience overview (October 2015 – December 2016)

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Location

Oct 1, 2015 - Dec 26, 2016

Customize Email Export Add to Dashboard Shortcut

All Users
100.00% Sessions

+ Add Segment

Map Overlay Explorer

Summary Site Usage Ecommerce

Sessions

Primary Dimension: Country City Continent Sub Continent

Secondary dimension

advanced

Country	Acquisition			Behavior			Conversions		
	Sessions	% New Sessions	New Users	Bounce Rate	Pages / Session	Avg. Session Duration	Goal Conversion Rate	Goal Completions	Goal Value
	4,671 % of Total: 100.00% (4,671)	71.18% Avg for View: 71.12% (0.09%)	3,325 % of Total: 100.09% (3,322)	72.60% Avg for View: 72.60% (0.00%)	2.37 Avg for View: 2.37 (0.00%)	00:02:09 Avg for View: 00:02:09 (0.00%)	0.00% Avg for View: 0.00% (0.00%)	0 % of Total: 0.00% (0)	\$0.00 % of Total: 0.00% (\$0.00)
1. Russia	1,672 (35.80%)	87.20%	1,458 (43.85%)	98.56%	1.01	00:00:09	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
2. Greece	746 (15.97%)	27.61%	206 (6.20%)	32.04%	5.11	00:08:20	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
3. Germany	388 (8.31%)	72.94%	283 (8.51%)	61.34%	4.39	00:02:57	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
4. United Kingdom	375 (8.03%)	65.60%	246 (7.40%)	49.87%	2.73	00:01:55	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
5. Kyrgyzstan	187 (4.00%)	79.14%	148 (4.45%)	96.79%	1.05	00:00:20	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
6. Belgium	168 (3.60%)	80.36%	135 (4.06%)	55.95%	2.71	00:01:32	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
7. Sweden	161 (3.45%)	57.76%	93 (2.80%)	53.42%	2.57	00:01:38	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
8. United States	129 (2.76%)	89.92%	116 (3.49%)	84.50%	1.41	00:00:23	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
9. Spain	75 (1.61%)	74.67%	56 (1.68%)	61.33%	2.25	00:01:04	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
10. Italy	65 (1.39%)	83.08%	54 (1.62%)	55.38%	2.35	00:02:13	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)

Show rows: 10 Goto: 1 1 - 10 of 79

This report was generated on 12/27/16 at 12:23:16 PM - Refresh Report

Figure 2 : Location overview (October 2015 – December 2016)

APPENDIX III – Facebook Page Insights

Insights is a free service for all Facebook Pages and Facebook Platform application and websites. Facebook Insights provides Facebook Page owners and Facebook Platform developers with metrics around their content.

Below are the most important data retrieved from SENSE4US Facebook page Insights for the reporting period from October 2015 (M25) to December 2016 (M39):

Figure 3 : Number of people the posts reached (October 2015-December 2016)

Time	Post Content	Reach	Engagement	Boost Post
5:55 pm	US ce the project's upcoming confe	0	0	Boost Post
11/01/2016 1:31 pm	ITProPortal - The rise of Open D ata and why it's important #Ope	8	1	Boost Post
10/17/2016 5:04 pm	SENSE4US Lessons from Seoul: How eGov ernment can drive citizen engag	12	2	Boost Post
10/11/2016 1:01 pm	SENSE4US Joinup - Public review of Germa n municipal eGovernment mana	9	0	Boost Post
10/04/2016 11:49 am	European Commission - EU eG overnment Report 2016 shows t	258	86	Boost Post

Figure 4 : The post that most people reached within the reporting period (4th October 2016)

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Total Page Likes as of Today: 124

Figure 5 : Total Page Likes

Figure 6 : SENSE4US audience overview (December 2016)

APPENDIX IV – Twitter Profile Overview (Hootsuite)

In D8.7 we use the Hootsuite tool in order to present SENSE4US Twitter Profile Overview as it provides free analytics reports for longer periods in comparison to Klout and other Analytic tools.

Hootsuite is a Social Media Management System that helps its users to keep track and manage their social network channels. Multiple networks such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Google+ can be managed at the same time. Moreover it provides Analytic tools for users' profiles

Below are the most important data retrieved from Hootsuite tool concerning SENSE4US Twitter profile for the reporting period from October 2015 (M25) to December 2016 (M39):

Figure 7 : SENSE4US Twitter Profile Summary (October 2015 - December 2016)

Figure 8 : Follower Growth (October 2015 - December 2016)

Most Popular Links

Rank	Date	Post	Clicks
1	Apr 1, 2016	http://ow.ly/ZR5d1 http://www.energysavingtrust.org.uk/blog/2016/0... Learn the benefits of buying #electriccars: http://ow.ly/ZR5d1 Advice for both businesses and individuals. #EVsvia @EnergySvngTrust	31 clicks
2	May 6, 2016	http://ow.ly/4nu7f9 http://www.theguardian.com/public-leaders-netwo... The Guardian: Five ways open data can boost democracy around the world #opendata http://ow.ly/4nu7f9	15 clicks
3	Jun 15, 2016	http://ow.ly/AfaR301h7zq http://www.sense4us.eu/index.php/blog/234-upcom... Upcoming: 16th European Conference on eGovernment http://ow.ly/AfaR301h7zq	9 clicks
4	May 23, 2016	http://ow.ly/KrFu300tmdy http://www.sense4us.eu/index.php/blog/217-open-... Open Knowledge - DEMOCRATISING THE DATA REVOLUTION: A DISCUSSION PAPER by Jonathan Gray http://ow.ly/KrFu300tmdy	7 clicks
5	Mar 16, 2016	http://ow.ly/Ztm4g http://www.europeandataportal.eu/en/content/gol... Becoming a front runner in #OpenData requires a strategy. But how do you get there? http://ow.ly/Ztm4g	6 clicks
6	May 16, 2016	http://ow.ly/XjPv300egPC http://www.sense4us.eu/index.php/blog?platform=... SENSE4US project has joined as a member the European Centre for Social Media http://ow.ly/XjPv300egPC	5 clicks
7	Feb 3, 2016	http://ow.ly/X55MQ http://www.sense4us.eu/index.php/news-letter?pl... Some interesting news is part of our newsletter issue along with some events http://ow.ly/X55MQ #data #policy	4 clicks
8	Jun 1, 2016	http://ow.ly/EzKe300N4Nw http://www.sense4us.eu/index.php/blog/221-occd-... OECD COMPARATIVE STUDY - REBOOTING PUBLIC SERVICE DELIVERY #opendata #innovation http://ow.ly/EzKe300N4Nw	4 clicks
9	Mar 20, 2016	http://ow.ly/ZF2DJ http://opendatacon.org/roadmap2016/ This is the #OpenData Roadmap of 2015. Will you contribute to the roadmap of #IODC16? http://ow.ly/ZF2DJ	4 clicks
10	Feb 9, 2016	http://ow.ly/Y4Ab9 http://www.sense4us.eu/index.php/blog/148-ovied... Oviedo reuses Madrids #citizens #participation tool http://ow.ly/Y4Ab9	3 clicks

Figure 9 : Most Popular Links (October 2015 - December 2016)